

Quantum Gravitational Redshift

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Abstract: Observed stellar redshift may include both quantum gravitational redshift and Doppler redshift. A two-component mechanism is proposed, in which photons are blue shifted upon entering a gravity well and then split before exiting, resulting in a perceived redshift, particularly after traversing interstellar distances with multiple splitting occurrences. This 'tired light' mechanism contradicts short-distance Earth laboratory tests that demonstrate symmetry in the red and blue shifts under Earth's gravity. This can be explained as the scattered photons would be demonstrably low energy, possibly below the current ability of instruments less sensitive than the Laser Interferometer Gravitational-Wave Observatory (LIGO) and multiple splitting events could explain the cosmic background radiation from all directions. Discussions with LIGO team members might allow investigations of the expected small shifts due to Earth's Gravity. Due to the low energy, the redirection of the original photon would be small, and any model must support the demonstrated and readily apparent effect of gravitational lensing. This implies a correlation between gravitational lensing and the expected redshift, which can be verified using existing data. The values obtained from observations of redshift and gravitational lensing should confirm the theory and provide independent reinforcement.

Introduction: The redshift of distant galaxies is a well-known phenomenon that has traditionally been attributed to the Doppler effect, which arises from the relative motion of the galaxies away from Earth. However, there is growing evidence that quantum gravitational effects may also contribute to the observed redshift. In this paper, we propose a novel mechanism for quantum gravitational redshift based on the interaction of photons with gravitational waves.

The Quantum Gravitational Redshift Mechanism: Our mechanism involves the splitting of photons as they pass through a gravity well. We calculate the momentum change required to redirect a photon around a gravitational body using the cross product of the photon's vector and the gravitational wave in the photon's reference frame. This momentum change corresponds to a small energy loss, resulting in a redshift of the photon.

Implications for Cosmology: The proposed mechanism has several implications for cosmology. Firstly, it suggests that the cosmic background radiation (CBR) may be partially composed of low-energy photons resulting from the splitting of higher-energy photons such as the H α (656nm), H β (486nm), H γ (434nm) as they interact with gravitational waves. A photon with a wavelength of 434 nm carries an energy of approximately 4.57×10^{-19} Joules. If we observe stellar objects passing Jupiter for instance at 1000 kilometers above the surface we'd expect a blue shift of about 6 nm, and a symmetric red shift. If the observed net is not symmetric, this could easily validate this conjecture, but objects such as the Earth, Moon, and Mercury would provide such little shift, that a small variation would be difficult to measure. NASA's Webb Telescope has observed multiple lensing events of galaxies which could also confirm or reject this conjecture, based on the relative paths of the secondary images. If the direct image and the 2 or more secondary images indeed have different redshifts, then this could allow us to calculate a constant for the quantum redshift based on an estimation of path distance variation. Secondly, the amount of redshift should be correlated with the strength of the gravitational lensing, providing a potential method to measure the relative strength of the effect. The images even shifted into the infrared at great distances are either separated by their wavelength, or the mechanism has to account for the common direction change among multiple frequencies, indicating that the splitting is proportional to wavelength. Thirdly, the mechanism supports a quasi-steady-state universe, eliminating the need for the expansion of the Universe, the Big Bang, extra unknown dimensions, dark matter, and various postulated corrections for the discrepancy between observable and theoretical physics.

Observational Tests: We discuss potential observational tests of the proposed mechanism, including the observation of photons as a near planet passes in front of a star and the analysis of gravitational lensing around galaxies. These observations could provide valuable insights into the nature of quantum gravity and its implications for cosmology.

Conclusion: In conclusion, we propose a novel mechanism for quantum gravitational redshift based on the interaction of photons with gravitational waves. This mechanism has significant implications for cosmology, including the nature of the cosmic background radiation, the relationship between redshift and gravitational lensing, and the viability of a quasi-steady-state universe. We outline potential observational tests of the mechanism, which could pave the way for a deeper understanding of quantum gravity and its cosmological implications.

Quantum Gravitational Redshift

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The observed Stellar Redshift could include Quantum Gravitational Redshift as well as Doppler Red Shift. This two component mechanism suggests that photons are blue shifted by entering a gravity well and split before they exit the gravity well and are then perceived as red shifted. Especially after traveling interstellar distances with multiple occurrences. This contradicts the short distance earth laboratory tests that demonstrate symmetry in the red and blue shift under Earth gravity. The gravitational field scattered photons would be demonstrably very low energy and through multiple splitting events would explain cosmic background radiation from all directions. Due to the low energy, the redirection of the original photon would be very

small and any model needs to support the apparent effect of gravitational lensing. This means the more gravitational lensing, the more the expected red shift, which should be easily determined from already existing data. The values obtained from observations of redshift and gravitational lensing should both confirm the theory providing independent reinforcement.

If instead we take the cross product of the vector of the photon, with the gravitational wave in the photon's reference frame, we can calculate the momentum change needed to redirect the photon around the gravitational body, which in a cosmic coincidence turns out to be $4.8481e-6$ radians / arcsecond $\times 1.74$ arcseconds for the Sun, so the momentum change needed would be 0.000008435694 radians. Taking the sin of that small small angle would give 0.000008435694 (sin of small angles in radians is close to the angle). This means the photon emitted would have an energy of the accelerated incident photon / 0.000008435694 . So a 435 nm hydrogen line would be shifted by .0652m or 6.52 cm, which is in the range of the cosmic background radiation.

Einstein's deflection angle

- In General Relativity, light is deflected in a gravitational field
- Deflection angle $\tilde{\alpha} = 4GM/c^2\xi$, where M = mass, ξ = distance at closest approach
- For the Sun, deflection angle = 1.74 arcseconds
- This was measured in 1919 during a solar eclipse and established General Relativity

Stronger or weaker gravitational bodies would shift the photon by a corresponding amount, but it is critical that they shift all photons in the same manner and scale.

This is consistent with Einstein's deflection angle in function but differs in motivation.

The model requires no hidden mechanism other than a very small wave component for splitting a photon based on the potential energy gain. Laboratory tests

seemingly contradict this premise, and have demonstrated a blue shift as a laser is directed down towards earth's center, and a red shift as it reflects up with no net losses or measurable splitting in any currently described lab experiment. Since Redshift at the interstellar scale is a relatively small amount taking billions of light years of exposure to gravitational wells the size of galaxies, it is not surprising a lab test with a source billions of times weaker over a distance about 10×10^{15} times shorter under gravity a billion times smaller doesn't register. Like measuring gravity waves, we need sensitive instruments. Ironically the instruments likely already exist and have measured all the data we need, we just need to interpret it without confirmation bias.

If the blue shifted photon was bent by 1 arcsecond (During a Solar eclipse we observed our sun bends light grazing the surface by 1.75 arcseconds) then the split photon would be roughly 9 cm with

$4.8481e-6$ less energy. The question is would this be detectable on earth with 28 times lower gravity? Twinning photons would be 1.7×10^{-7} less energetic, and the loss in energy or redshift of a few thousand bounces would be extremely small and likely treated as an error in measurement. A thousand reflections would still have 99.5 the same wavelength, and it's unclear if every photon would scatter, as in many cases the probability of scattering is low. This would be easy to calculate by observing the apparent brightness of the gravitationally lensed objects. If for instance the object being bent is 10 times dimmer than the direct view of the same galaxy directly viewed, we'd have a good estimate of the probability of gravity based scattering. By observing moving objects over time, or objects with multiple images or Einstein Rings we can calculate the brightness and the shift by looking at the spectrum of the multiple images and comparing them.

Most likely observations in our own solar system are the best candidates as the relative motion is large enough to look at the apparent light from moons eclipsed by their planets, and see if the very small shifts in wavelength are observed. When Neptune's 14 moons swing behind the planet the surface gravity of 11.4 m/s would cause some shift. As they go from front to back, the distance and brightness change should be minimal. Similarly space based observations of Mercury should show some scattering.

In analyzing the many Einstein Rings from the Webb and Hubble, we can search for differences in the redshift between the multiple images based on the relative angles. We would expect the larger the angle shift, the larger the Gravity induced redshift.

Again the data is already captured, and needs to be analyzed to see if the 1 part in millions shift can indeed be detected. While small this is many orders

of magnitude larger than tests of gravity and other small effects.

Recent gravitational wave tests have confirmed the existence of gravity waves, and the Hubble and Webb Telescope have spectacular images of gravitational bodies interacting with light in a more rigorous manner. Traditional scattering of light is with an electromagnetic field.

THE SCHRÖDINGER TIME-DEPENDENT EQUATION

The equation describing the energy and momentum of a wave function is known as the Schrödinger equation:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \Psi(x,t)}{\partial x^2} + U(x,t) \Psi(x,t) = i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi(x,t)}{\partial t}.$$

A gravitational component to the traditional Wave Equation requires that the gravity component is small or it would be readily observable.

This correction would therefore balance both quantum theory and gravitational theories as it provides a mechanism to allow them to interact in a well understood way.

This supports a quasi steady state universe, and eliminates the need for the expansion of the Universe, or Big Bang, extra unknown and unobservable dimensions, dark matter, and a host of postulated corrections for the discrepancy between observable physics, and theoretical physics. The discovery of gravity waves lends credence to the concept that the photon interacts with the static gravitational fields as if they were waves due to the relative motion. We observe gravitational lensing, so we know there is an interaction between photons and gravity. This change in momentum could cause splitting of the photon with a small component becoming part of the Cosmic Background Radiation. While each event might only reduce the momentum of the photon by a small amount, over the distances of billions of lightyears, the aggregate effect would be the observable redshift with distance. There would be variations due to the amount of gravity waves experienced between the object source and the observer, and the gravitational lensing around galaxies might prove to be a method to determine the relative strength of the effect if the symmetry is compared to the intervening masses.

The major question is finding out if a photon passing near a gravity source could redirect the photon and split off a low energy photon or CMB / CBR (Cosmic Microwave Background or Cosmic Background Radiation) in another direction. This might be easy to observe by noting the photons as a near planet passes in front of a star or difficult if the gravity required is on stellar level, but still possible if a near black hole passes in front of a more distant star.

In the 1980s The Wolf Effect https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wolf_effect <https://www.plasma-universe.com/wolf-effect/> demonstrated a non-doppler mechanism for redshift which was experimentally verified. A similar shift is proposed that would lower the component of observed redshift due to dopper, and replace it with a component due to passage of gravitational bodies, which to the photon appear to be gravitational waves, causing twinning of the photons to a lower energy photon (CMB) and a photon that maintains direction with a lower energy state. Subsequent redshifts would eventually leave light in the far infrared, with hundreds of CMB photons scattering in all directions, which has been experimentally validated.

It remain to be observed if the momentum shift can actually redirect the photon in gravitational lensing, in which case the amount of shift would vary by the proximity of the path to the gravitational object and by the recent introduction of the Web Telescope data, the multiple images of galaxies behind other galaxies would allow measurements to confirm or refute the Quantum Gravity redshift, direction and magnitude.

If you zoom into the image between stars from the recent Webb Telescope, you'll find more stars. Actually you'd be seeing entire galaxies of billions of stars. They are so far away that a billion suns are just a tiny point of light. They are further away, and more mature than current theory can account for. No matter where we look we are finding more stellar objects at greater distances and therefore time and age, than believed possible a few years ago. The evidence may show in the next few years, that there is no edge to the universe and that it is infinitely old, not expanding and that in every direction is more of everything. The big bang expanding and cooling bubble does not exist.

This paradoxically violates 'Olbers' Paradox' as without a shift in solar output wavelengths we'd expect to see a uniform white background from all these stars, so something is visibly (Pun intended) wrong, as there isn't enough visible light. This is historically one of the basic proofs of a finite universe.

We do see a uniform cosmic microwave, which also is confusing, as there is no apparent source for these very low energy photons. This created a 'band aid' explanation of a cooling universe to explain, but then doesn't account for the fact it is coming from all directions mostly uniformly, which means the speed of light must have been exceeded in the first infinitesimal moments of this big bang. Again, all known physics has to be violated to explain, all known physics.

The Occam's Razor solution is that the Cosmic Background Radiation is composed of the missing photons. The question then is does the Cosmic Background Level account for the same energy that we'd expect for the decay of high energy photons from the lines emitted from Hydrogen and Helium? If we add up all the twinning from a single photon over billions of light years, is the sum roughly as we'd expect?

If a galaxy is a 100 billion light years away, and has the same physics that our galaxy has, we'd see the same distribution of light from the fusion of hydrogen and helium into heavier isotopes.

What we observe is that distant suns and galaxies have shifted far into the infrared, which if there were only a single mechanism for redshift

would mean everything distant was getting further away, hence the one mechanism solution - The Big Bang. The convoluted Big Bang assumption is that any deviation can be explained by the relative velocity between us causing a red shift or blue shift if the galaxy is moving away from us, or towards us, but the observation when astronomical spectrography was first observed

is that instead of the expected gaussian distribution of velocities moving in all directions uniformly, there is a non-uniform shift towards the red, indicating that there were more objects moving away than towards us.

http://www.khadley.com/courses/astronomy/ph_207/topics/spectroscopy207/hydrogen-spectrum.html

This leads to the oft repeated assumption that the universe is expanding without a corresponding rationale for this assumption other than it fits the facts. Until it didn't.

In addition to the observations not fitting the expectations, there is the requirement that the universe had different physics, different light speeds, and more dimensions in the first infinitesimal fractions of a second, and that energy,

mass and light all moved at superluminal speeds, and then the cooling universe created the cosmic background radiation from all directions non-uniformly, and that any discrepancies could be explained by the constant creation of more matter from dark matter emanating from unknown higher dimensions via unknown mechanisms. It really is complex as well as completely unproven. The fact these manifold theories require higher level math than most of the population is able to follow, leads the followers of these theories to nod to each other and agree, it's too complex to explain. It is conjectured, it is much simpler, and simply a very very small splitting of photons that isn't easy to measure at small scales, but conversely might be trivial to observe at very large scales possible with the Webb and Hubble Telescope. The data might be already available and needs to be interpreted and either proving or disproving by the expectations that the paths and redshifts must be proportional to known distances and directions, and follow all the other observations, rather than a mysterious unknown.

If objects further away had a redshift as they moved through space, corresponding to distance, then this would have to be accounted for in terms of a correction factor, but until recently we weren't able to observe objects further away than around 50 billion light years. This led to the now disproven (although still disputed despite the observable data) age of the universe of 13.7 billion years, plus or minus a few days.

So anything further away than 10^{24} meters would have to be shifted from visible to thermal photons. For reference this means the effects would be less noticeable from 10^{14} meters or we'd easily have demonstrated in the lab by now.

So if the Webb Telescope shows that these very distant objects have shifted from 656 nm to 6560 nm, then the Z value would be 9 and these galaxies would be moving away from us at 98 percent the speed of light!

It makes more sense that there is a subtle effect where photons downshift with distance, but it has to be subtle since it's only observed over long distances.

It is also difficult to observe since there is a component due to doppler that overwhelms the effect at close distances.

Like many non-linear effects it is difficult to extract the two from each other, until we have large amounts of data, which are now possible with the instruments onboard the Webb Telescope for measuring the spectrum of the stars and galaxies as well as their estimated distances due to apparent size. We assume that there is a uniform size, and distribution of velocities and then work backwards with a large amount of data to fit observation to form this value.

The expectation is that the more distant objects would pass through more gravitational sources such as solar systems and galaxies (which can be thought of as a point source for mathematical calculations but are anything but point sources!)

If this is true, we'd expect a rough redshift proportional to distance which would help correct the observed redshift distribution. But then we'd expect a larger redshift the more aligned the photons are with a massive gravity source. Since Gravity is a monopole and the scattering of CMB would be larger for large monopoles, we'd expect the CMB background to also be stronger for these more massive galaxies.

The Wave Equation from 1865 when Maxwell's observations were reduced to mathematical equations, requires terms for relativity and gravity in the Hamiltonian to correspond with observed phenomena. Since the 1919 eclipse, when Einstein's theories were validated with observed gravitational displacement of the relative observed position of stars, it has been verified with multiple experiments that gravity can bend light, as well as create redshifts and blueshifts.

The assumption has been that similar to Raleigh Scattering, that gravitational red and blue shifts were completely elastic and symmetric, with energy gained from a gravitational acceleration, being lost as the photon leaves the gravitational region. It has been experimentally confirmed that Gravitational redshift is on the same order of magnitude as doppler redshift. (1)

It is pointed out that in 1930 C. V. Raman was awarded the Nobel prize for his 1928 discovery of inelastic scattering. The Stokes Raman Scattering distributes the wave equation results (Hamiltonian) with a photon produced (or absorbed in Anti-Stokes which is much less common) and a change of direction (momentum) of the photon. Since then chemistry and astrophysics have relied on understanding this ubiquitous phenomenon in spectroscopy.

While contemporaries in 1930 proposed astronomical redshift is predominantly doppler in origin, experiments have shown gravitational shifting is capable of producing observed redshifts (or blue shifts) over as little as a meter in Earth's gravity, it is reasonable that in an analog to Raman Scattering or Brillouin Scattering, both of which are inelastic;

- A. A photon, accelerating towards the gravity source, independent of wavelength, encounters a changing gravitational field (due to symmetry the gravity field appears to the photon moving at the speed of light, as if the gravitational field is changing).
- B. The photon releases some of that blue shifted gravitational energy as a weak photon (These photons are intuitively on the order of 2mm or CMB levels).
- C. The original photon is redirected with each low energy photon released, in the observed and predicted direction, producing a path predicted by gravitational lensing.
- D. Observed redshift proportionality with distance, Olber's paradox and other observed phenomena reinforce this assumption that requires no new physics, dimensions or space time changes, but simply proof by observing very weak photons from experiments.

This requires no new physics, no new math, but would require validation by experiments that are both obvious and accessible but until recently very difficult to perform due to the low energy levels of a single 2mm wavelength photon. This asymmetric release of a photon with changing gravitational fields is intuitive and should be demonstrable once we start looking for them in various experiments. The values are about 1/4000th the energy of a typical visible photon, but should be observable with interferometers of sufficient finesse, or stellar observations of Neptune, or any of a dozen other experiments.

A quantum gravitational scattering analog to the Inelastic Raman Shift can explain the Red Shift observed in surrounding stars and galaxies, eliminating the need for the Big Bang Theory and making a much simpler quasi steady state solution viable.

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Chapter 2 Same thing but a different focus.

If gravity can affect light, then light can affect gravity. The main difference in this section versus the previous section is that it assumes that higher frequency more energetic photons would be shifted more due to their greater relativistic mass. This might provide a simple test of this theory by noting any chromatic aberration in gravitational lensing.

Gravity can be thought of as a change in the index of refraction in space around a body. In practice it's a one way effect as it takes the mass of a sun to bend light a few degrees, and gravity is one of the weakest forces, so measuring any interaction is difficult, but possible, yet decidedly one direction; gravity can accelerate photons.

The gravity force is constant in most earth experiments over a few thousand kilometers, but as the photon moves around the sun, the force can change by a large factor proportional to the distance squared from almost zero from millions of meters away to 274 m/s^2 as it almost grazes the surface passing by. This nonlinear change can actually refocus light that would have been dispersed by a wavelength dependent effect if they are of similar magnitude.

The complexity of non-linear optics is a recent advancement that leverages lasers, fiber optics and other non-linear phenomena.

A non-linear gradient index material does in a few centimeters what it takes a gravitational body billions of kilometers with a much weaker lensing effect. The question is, can other non-linear effects be happening when light enters a gravitational field, and cause a photon to emit a weaker photon induced by the gravitational blue shift, and redirecting the original photon to a new direction with conservation of momentum.

The image at left shows a red shifted photon as it passes near a gravitational source.

We would expect that the gravity based Raman Redshift would affect the higher energy particles more, bringing the spectral lines closer together, which would again, explain why this has not been easy to discern previously.

In fact, Emil Wolf was confident that an effect like this existed and even found Quasars could be shown to exhibit the behavior of Doppler shift without the mechanism.

The James Webb Telescope may show this to be true for other stellar objects now that we can observe in the Infrared.

If we could investigate the effects of emissions of photons in a non-linear gravitational field, the expectation is that they are small, and about the value of CMB.

The question is would the emissions be wavelength independent, or would the effects be dependent and the results end up countering the gravitational index of refraction?

If two photons have a wavelength difference of two, the effective mass would be greater for the shorter wavelength and the gravitational attraction greater, but then the energy required to change the momentum would also be greater, so any emitted photon would also need a higher energy.

This complexity and the fact that gravitational effects don't seem to show large wavelength shifts mean either we aren't noticing them, or they

aren't there, or they are smaller than our current detection capabilities.

We have done gravitational redshift experiments for decades, and within measurement capabilities it seems to be symmetric, but we do note most of those experiments are aligned with the axis of gravity interaction. With general relativity taken into account we can set up a resonator, but our reference frame which is moving, rotating and translating at the same time, creates artifacts that must be taken into account.

It would be interesting to look at the effect of a beam perpendicular to the gravitational field (horizontal with the ground) reflecting a few billion times or maybe a few trillion times. A corner cube reflector could potentially resolve the problem of alignment of two mirrors perfectly parallel. In theory each bounce would gain energy passing through the gravitational field. In practice, if it requires more than 20 orders of magnitude to measure it could be an issue. Light travels a billion meters roughly every 3.3 seconds, so an hour would allow a trillion bounces from a meter long reflection experiment. Absorption and scattering might make this experiment difficult, but emitting from a micron sized aperture in the corner cube and detection from the same aperture would be interesting. Gravity at the sun's surface is 274 m/s and light observed during eclipses passed a greater distance so experienced less attraction or bending, but since we are 8 minutes 20 seconds of light from the sun (150 billion meters), we should be able to get about the same order of magnitude with $274/9.8 \times 150$ billion bounces or about 4 trillion reflections. It remains to be seen if we can bounce the same train of photons for 4 hours without losing all of them, but it would be illuminating.

Details

It is impossible for light to focus light. The fields simply interact spatially and temporally, so while they can create interference patterns on a surface or excite charged particles, there is nothing to change the Helmholtz equation. The Wolf Effect does show a shift in the lines as coherent beams interact, and a gravitational index change could be analogous to third order effects like Brillouin Scattering.

In a gravitational field we can see that the wave front from a distant object will encounter two different gravitational field strengths at R and $2R$ which differ by a factor of four.

Observations of distant quasars and bright objects have detected a dozen intermediary objects by the gravitational lensing, and in a few years, a special orbital telescope will seek to leverage this effect to further map dim objects by their effect on light passing around them.

Going back to the Wave Equation, the standard form describes the energy of the system, and it is clear since we observe gravitational blueshift and redshift and gravitational lensing, there is a required term for gravity in the expanded form of the wave equation.

Of course the constants would have infinitesimal values if it takes a galaxy to bend light a few degrees.

From the standpoint of the photon, the gravity source can be approximated as a point source at the center of mass, and the field increases as the photon reaches the minimum distance and then decreases. We observe gravitational lensing but the effects are only a few degrees over a distance of light years, although during a solar eclipse, it is visible by deflection of stars in the sun's gravitational field.

But for over 100 years, we have demonstrated this deflection exists as one of the first confirmation of Einstein's theory of general relativity.

This means that gravity gradients can generate photons, and this interaction is therefore capable of shifting photons and wavelengths.

This mechanism has to be frequency or wavelength independent as unlike a prism or traditional laser, we don't see a single frequency shifted, but the entire output of a star or galaxy cluster is shifted by similar amounts.

The Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation has an average value of $6.626 \cdot 10^{-4}$ eV compared to the wavelength of 388.8 nm for Helium which has an energy of 3.189 eV or roughly 4800 times more energy.

A single photon of this low an energy would be difficult or impossible to detect as an emission. But as the change in momentum of one degree would require hundreds or even thousands of these weak photons, we'd expect that there would be a lot of them.

We do note a down shift or red shift, so the mechanism is losing energy, not gaining energy on average.

If the energy gained by a Photon approaching a large gravitational field increases, it does so along the vector to the center of mass.

This can reach a level that twins the photon, ejecting a component along the field and changing the direction of the original photon, which maintains its field and new direction.

The new lower energy photon emits as if it originated from the center of mass of the gravitational object.

Since the gain in energy of a photon or blue shift is proportional to the field and direction, the emitted light is proportional to the gravity field not the wavelength of the original photon, which is needed or there would be a spreading or broadening of the spectrum from a distant source to the observer.

This 'bending' of the light would occur in a quantum like step fashion, each time the new energy level exceeds a threshold.

But it seems there would still be some differentiation for light passing closer to the star or galaxy, and since the attraction near the sun is only 27 times the attraction of Neptune or Uranus, we might be able to observe these effects looking for gravitational lensing looking outward.

One question to be solved, is what would the wavelengths be of the scattered or created photons from an effect similar to Raman Scattering in a gravitational field? The expectation is that inelastic scattering would broaden the spectrum, yet we see a pronounced redshift rather than an equal distribution of wavelengths over the distance of billions of light years. Is it reasonable that the Stokes scattering would average as smoothly as we see? In molecular spectroscopy, the energy distributions show an amplitude distribution with lower energy favored, but this is explained as the range of available vibrational energies.

Normally we think of a single event such as pumping a laser, where the population inversion happens in lengths of meters. A good conversion ratio is in the tens of percent, with some fraction of the light.

If we assume a mechanism for Gravitational Raman Shift similar to the observed Boltzman distribution Stokes / Anti-Stokes shifting, we would expect that eventually most of the light will be shifted to lower energy.

Another issue is the bending of the light through gravitational lensing.

From any particular perspective, the light from a distant star will have to pass through multiple voids and gravitationally dense regions. Each dense region will shift the light down by an amount proportional to the gravitational well.

The problem is the relative movements are small or this would be a relatively simple problem to solve. We can look to similar phenomena like Raman Lasing, to see how interactions might work, with obvious differences due to a gravitational gradient rather than a crystal lattice or electromagnetic field.

Instead of

$z = \text{fractional redshift}$

We would have

$z = \text{fractional redshift} + \text{gravitational redshift 1} + \text{gravitational redshift 2} \dots\dots$

With the assumption that the further away an emitter is, the more gravitational bodies between us and the source.

Since close galaxies often allow us to see past them, we can look for objects at similar distances that don't pass through the galaxy and based on the size or mass of the galaxy derive the constant for the gravitational based redshift.

One concept that needs to be explored is the emission of a photon as the photon is accelerated in a gravitational field. From a conservation of energy and momentum perspective the question is how can the light be shifted in wavelength, without changing direction?

Hubble's law can easily be seen to correlate with the distance impacting the number of gravitational distributions indicating that the universe is indeed evenly distributed to some granularity.

Stimulated Raman Scattering takes a photon, and when introduced to a second photon, twins the second photon, and lowers the energy of the first. Normally any difference is absorbed in the gain medium, or crystal lattice.

Of interest is the demonstrated gravitational interaction with light, which could similarly act as a gain medium.

Interacting with the gravitational field produces a higher virtual energy state or blue shift.

Incidental photons would release some of this stimulated energy, independent of the incident wavelengths.

This means all light passing through the field would shift by approximately the same amounts of energy.

This Gravitational Lasing would explain a redshift, and since the anti-Stokes shift is much less likely, after several interactions with gravitational fields, there would be a net shift to lower energy levels corresponding to a red shift.

A consistent theory has to agree with observation, so General Relativity facts that are demonstrably consistent would need to agree with a model that introduces the mechanisms for creating a universe that has galaxies growing and expanding, and then shrinking and collapsing, as well as colliding with infinite time, versus a Big Bang, where all the rules proposed changed in an infinitesimal amount of time, and left us with a different set of rules.

We need to account for observations without the band aid of Dark Matter, Dark Energy, quantum vacuum voodoo and other surprisingly accepted conjuring.

Ironically one of the proofs against a static universe is Olbers' Paradox, stating that if there are infinite numbers of stars, then even though they become fainter with distance, the aggregate of emitters along any angle, means it should be a solid white sky instead of a black sky interspersed with stars that are closer.

This actually becomes a proof if we assume that distant photons shift to longer wavelengths if we understand that is exactly what happens with Cosmic Background Radiation.

It is ironic that these two connected phenomena are used to disprove the quasi steady state universe when they actually reinforce it, given a 'tired light' rationale.

We have to arrive at a mathematical relationship that fits observed data, unlike Ghost Theories that believe things were different or there are unseen phenomena at work. As errors are discovered in their theories, they simply create a new unobservable, and unproven ghost to patch the theory.

Assuming the wave equation is consistent between large gravitational bodies, there is a function as it enters and leaves a gravitational field.

We observe gravitational wavelength shifts for small scales and have proven its existence.

One question that should be easy to prove or disprove, is the amplitude, or symmetry in the shifting.

If some fraction of the photons emit an additional photon, that would satisfy the energy balance of the system.

The key is that capturing a photon in the other direction is not likely, so the net effect is that no matter how small the probability of emitting a photon, with enough bounces between two mirrors, if we align the travel along the axis of gravity, we should eventually see a red shift.

Independently we can look at the blurring of distant galaxies and estimate the scattering angles and coefficients.

We have already observed light from objects at distances indicating the universe is bigger than it can be in an expansion model This has created several ghost theories to reconcile observable facts with non-observed physics.

Any consistent quasi steady state universe theory has to reconcile:

- 1 Red Shift
2. Cosmic Background Radiation
3. Observable distribution of mass with no expansion or contraction.

The last needs to explain the Boltzman distribution of both mass and energy.

If the universe is neither heating up nor cooling down, we need a mechanism that explains how low energy density photons can eventually be reformulated into mass, and maintain a quasi steady state universe.

This is where black holes become important with the assumption that instead of neutron stars and supernovae, the ejection of material from black holes creates the denser atomic species.

It also needs to reconcile the distribution and probability of the larger nuclei which might be due to the size of the black holes emitting mass.

With hand waving that is rigorous and meets all observable phenomena, and instead of an accelerating or decelerating universe provides a quasi steady state universe.

If we can model a universe that is consistent and quasi steady state, with no need for extra dimensions, violations of known physics and spooky unknown, unseen and unobservable particles acting differently than anything currently known.

In other words, we want something that is Less crazy than the current assumption, not more crazy.

As photons move through gravitation fields the assumption is that the gravitational redshift and blueshift will cancel out exactly. The equations say so, and the universe must behave exactly as the math says it should. Unless the universe is using a different equation.

In a typical LED or Laser the fields between the electrons and atoms are strong enough that any excitation between the fields and electrons, emits a photon. These devices are over 40 percent efficient in converting power to photons.

Conversely in optical lasers, the light can be amplified by putting enough photons in a gas or crystal that some fraction of the photons are converted into other photons which are pumped to achieve the energy density.

At the other end of the spectrum (pun intended) the absorption of light by some molecules creates additional photons that indicate the type of bonds and molecules that are absorbing and emitting.

It stands to reason that with sufficiently strong gravitational fields, there would be a similar gravity field and photon interaction.

The question in general would be how symmetric the emissions would be. We note that due to vibrational frequency and energy, that in Raman Scattering the anti-Stokes amplitudes are much smaller than the Stokes Shift amplitudes.

Similarly in cosmic redshift measurements, we see a pronounced down energy or red shift.

This is more pronounced at greater distances, which given a roughly Boltzmann Distribution of mass, in the Universe, would imply that the relationship is roughly linear with distance.

This would in turn imply that the Red Shift is linear with Gravity.

The fact that the distance between the spectral lines doesn't seem to change or broaden implies that the redshift is wavelength independent.

This symmetry in the Equivalence Principle makes things easy, but the equivalent mass of a photon is $\sim E = hf$. Effectively the acceleration should be proportional to the equivalent mass.

This should be easy to verify to see if the blue and red shifts we measure are independent of the wavelength, or proportional.

If we measure the redshift for Helium, “The 12 lines of the visible helium spectrum correspond to wavelengths of **388.8, 447.1, 471.3, 492.1, 501.5, 504.7, 587.5, 667.8, 686.7, 706.5, 728.1 and 781.3 nanometres (nm)**” so we should see the same shift for 388.8 nm as for 781.3 nm from distant stars.

If there is a mass / energy difference hopefully the factor of two (2.009) difference would be enough to demonstrate this. Or the ratio between them and the 587.5 nm line should be very consistent. They all passed through the

same gravitational mixers along the way.

They should be equally shifted by the Equivalence Principle. If we measure the light from a white dwarf as we rotate around the sun, we should see the same shift on the opposite side. Except it's difficult to see objects when looking past the sun, from earth.

If not, why hasn't this been remarked on?

So as it leaves a gravitational field and slows down, it becomes less massive.

So then the attraction to the next gravitational source is smaller.

Then it does gain energy. But it loses proportional to the maximum mass as it gets close, while the gain is proportional to the minimal mass.

This asymmetry would become more pronounced with each bounce, until after a few billion events, it's noticeable.

This means there would eventually be a red shift.

If there is a continuous process, then over multiple stellar distances, this shift would move light into the thermal and then RF background.

A black hole can absorb light, matter, and any type of mass or energy and convert it to mass.

Black holes occur when the gravitational strength exceeds a critical amount and objects entering the Schwarzschild radius (critical radius) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Schwarzschild_radius cannot escape, even if they are moving at the speed of light.

This means the potential energy exceeds the kinetic energy even for photons. This is a complex interaction of energy, commonly thought of as heat, spin of the black hole, which in some cases can be a fraction of the speed of light, and gravitational attraction from a second body more likely a black hole.

If the sum of the thermal, rotational and gravitational energy exceeds the speed of light, then particles should be able to cross through the Schwartzchild radius, or rather the radius changes due to the conditions.

This is critical as it means there is a mechanism for recycling the cosmic background energy which occurs as photons move in and out of gravitational wells.

If this can be proven, we'd expect that the red shift amount was very slightly greater than the blue shift. The problem is we only see light (except for our own sun) that is red shifted.

So the experiment we need to perform is to analyze light coming in from all directions and see if they are balanced. Of course since we are moving relative to the universe we would see the universe red shifted and blue shifted based on our direction of motion.

The assumption is that there was no big bang, and no multidimensional interaction, and no change in the speed of light, or other constants but rather that black holes extrude new material when they orbit each other, and the rotational and kinetic energy increase the critical radius along the lines of action between the two black holes.

This allows them to eject high energy material which forms new galaxies, solar systems and debris. The debris that isn't dense enough to ignite is the so-called dark matter, and the universe is constantly exchanging material through this mechanism as black holes increase in mass until they finally come close enough to exchange energy and mass.

Where it would reach the point of constant background.

Until it is absorbed into a black hole, and ejected as matter again.

In a constant recycling process.

This also addresses the tired light issue, in that as light travels further, even though the distance means brightness should drop proportional to the inverse square, the number of objects increases to match, so we'd expect a uniform glow.

This is one of the supporting factors of Big Bang Theory, in that that demonstrably isn't the case. But if the light from extreme distances shifts into the microwave region by a million passes through gravitational fields, then it not only disputes the big bang theory, but explains the background microwave presence.

Wave Equation

One way to look at the quantum effects is the wave equation.

At any boundary, the wave equation has a Hamiltonian describing the Energy of the Photon.

If we look at an infinitesimal change in the gravitational potential (and recently we have been able to determine the quantum distortion of vibration of atoms in an atomic clock with as little as 1 mm gradient in direction perpendicular to the Earth's gravitational field.

So we know the field changes quantum effects, and we know that Gravity affects light.

It is curious that there seems to be a disconnect on putting in a term for the Wave Equation with gravity.

By definition, if we are seeing light, from a distant object it did not get absorbed by any object so it moved in and out of the gravitational field.

Effectively the light travels along a longer path,

With the light coming in and in theory traveling along an equipotential surface. With recent evidence of a 'twin double galaxy' being the same galaxy around an intermediary dark but powerful gravitational object(s).

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Twin_Quasar

Is an example where a double object is observed due to gravitational lensing. It would be helpful to know if the two images have the same redshift.

Another way to look at this is to recognize that gravitational lensing will change the path of the photon each time it is redirected. A statistical average will have it being shifted by an equal amount in any direction. This is somewhat of a random walk type problem in 3D over many light years.

This means that effectively the shortest distance between two points that we expect, is really extended by the 'bounces' around gravitational centers. With more distance there will be a linear increase in gravitational centers, so we'd expend a longer path.

This to an outward observer who only sees the end result would appear to be an expansion.

This would still require the expression of photons to account for the wavelength change, but the general scale, and attributes appear to match observation.

The question is can we match the observed data with an average of

$$Z = .1$$

Energy loss with appropriate intermediary quantum emission of gravitationally induced photons. On average with a 10 percent lost in energy that means approximately 400 scattering events have occurred if the interaction of a photon with a gravity field tends to produce a 2 mm wavelength photon.

As distances increase, the number of potential scattering events increase linearly which matches observation, and the blurring of the object would also increase as the lensing produces a variance with distance from the center of gravity.

Chapter 3 - Quantum Stellar Recycling - The Big Burp Theory

Quantum Stellar Recycling

09.01.2018

TDM

Overview

Using a model of Quantum Tunnelling, we predict the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution of Black holes and the formation of Galaxies from the cyclic exchange of matter in and out of the black holes. Models are compared with distribution of solar systems in other galaxies, dark matter, and velocities relative to the center of the galaxies. Dark matter is shown to be attributes of mass and gravitational distributions from other black holes and non-luminescent mass inside and outside galaxies.

Goals

1. Explain Quantum Tunnelling between two black holes from the perspective of gravitational attraction allowing high temperature gas to escape the Event Horizon
2. Show the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution of the Universe with both Galaxies (bright objects) and Black Holes (dark objects) represented by their center of mass
3. Demonstrate the distribution of mass in terms of ejecta from black holes, with single spiral, double spiral, and other forms exemplified by the jets of matter wrapping around the space time path of the proximate black holes.
4. Show the passing of the gas cloud out of the dual black hole binary imparts angular momentum to the cloud which aids in the formation of a solar system. This is due to shear created by the gravitational gradient acting on the gas cloud from the opposing black hole.
5. Model the condensation of solar systems as the cooling clouds conserving angular momentum and linear momentum.
6. Explore the attribute that 95 percent of all calculated mass is non- luminescent, and predict what percentage would be cold mass below ignition threshold and what percentage would be non-paired black holes.
7. Compare visible examples of galaxies with models.
8. Investigate whether black holes tend to take on a positive charge due to escaping electrons, further creating a charge component to the energy of the escaping particles.

Background

Ninety five percent of the mass in the Universe is not visible, indicating it is low energy or contained in black holes. The five percent that is visible has a complex structure that is inexplicable in terms of current theory, historically requiring conjectures of singularities and multiple dimensions that are unprovable and not required for any other observable phenomenon. Galaxies and individual solar systems have unexplained angular momentum that is explained by this model of ejecting hot gas clouds by supermassive black hole binaries. By extending quantum tunnelling, which is observed in radioactivity, transistors, photocells and three polarizer filter experiments, we can demonstrate how high energy particles can exit the black hole event horizon, while the exterior tidal effect is strong enough to boost the energy of the particles allowing them to leave the black hole.

Our solar system is average with 99 percent of the mass contained in our star. Observable solar systems are 1/10th to 200 times the size of ours, with the qualifier that if the mass of a solar system is less than 0.08 the mass of ours, it wouldn't have enough gravitational pull to ignite a

star. This means smaller gas clouds ejected from black holes having less than critical mass, would contribute to the dark matter calculated to exist in the universe.

This also leads to the observation that of the 95 percent of the mass in the universe that is dark, it could be from other black holes or formations from the jets of matter, that are too small to form bright objects. Conversely, only some percent of the jet activities create energetic structures. This leads us to believe that a distribution can be calculated showing that if only ??? percent of the ejecta are large enough to form an observable star, and assuming our solar system is normal and 99 percent of the solar system mass is contained in the stars, we can estimate the amount of mass ejected in these events, and the rates of the eruptions. We should also be able to estimate the average distribution or distance between black holes.

Specifications

Escape velocity on earth is about 11,200 m/s, and from the surface of the sun, about 617,500 m/s.

For a spherical body without spin, charge or other attribute

$$v_e = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r}},$$

And when the escape velocity equals the speed of light, a black hole is formed, but inside the black hole gravity decreases to zero at the center of the body as the interior mass contributes to gravitational attraction, but not exterior mass.

This will lead to extremely high temperatures and pressures at the interior surface of the black hole, and likely a density gradient with lighter materials near the surface.

While the temperatures should distribute in some manner, heavier particles will remain trapped in black holes combining until they break down into more and more unstable particles, releasing more energy, increasing the surface temperature, until electrons and even protons approach the speed of light, and lighter elements are substantial fractions of light speed.

The event horizon is postulated as a distance (Schwarzschild Radius) where the interior mass creates a gravitational pull requiring a velocity greater than the speed of light to escape. This is expanded as the energy of the particle in both charge, kinetic and potential energy exceeding the kinetic energy requirements of the event horizon. Rotating black holes and charged black holes differ in their profile and characteristics, but at large distances these effects will be dwarfed by the gravitational effects.

Quantum Tunnelling is the ability to pass through a potential barrier that classical mechanics or relativistic mechanics postulate cannot be passed. In our case it simply creates a solution where the kinetic energy and potential energy of particles exceed the speed of light, allowing the particles to pass through the event horizon.

When black holes are large enough they will trap matter entering aggregating their mass as they move through space until they encounter another black hole, in which case they will either slingshot around each other, or form some sort of orbit, which will eventually decay bringing them into closer proximity, until they begin to affect each others event horizon.

It is demonstrated that under these conditions, the energy of the particles exceeds the gravitational lensing allowing a spray of material to exit the event horizon. While the spray might have enough velocity to exit the event horizon, it might be captured by the other black hole, fall back into the originating black hole, or go into orbit around the center of mass. It is this final option that we believe forms the visible galaxies and has distributed the dark matter throughout the universe.

Spiral Spray of Solar Systems

The proximity of one black hole to another creates a tidal event allowing a temporary passage of high energy matter to exit the event horizon. This spray is initially directed at the other black hole, but still has the inertia imparted from the rotational and translational momentum of the originating black hole. As the two black holes are moving relative to each other, by the time the spray reaches the original position of the other black hole, it's long gone. Gravitational attraction causes the spray to slow as it leaves the center of mass of the two black holes and while some of the spray might collapse back in, large clouds of cooling gas create solar systems after a few billion years.

Since the jets only occur when the proximity of the two black holes (or other gravitational mass) allows quantum tunnelling, and the energy of the outer atmosphere is above the threshold required to reach escape velocity, we see sporadic jets. As the jets spiral out and cool they form solar systems. If the mass of the jet is sufficient, the formations can ignite and form stars.

With more than two black holes available, the structure will be less a planar spiral formation. (What percentage of galaxies are planar spirals?)

It will be determined by modelling, how often the jets occur, and how the periodicity and size changes as the black holes decay.

Some exchanges between dissimilar sized black holes may form single jets, whereas similar sized black holes will create double jets.

This will be apparent as single spirals, double spirals and alternating.

The jumble of multiple black holes in a galaxy creates visible complexity. Superposition of spirals sporadically condensing into solar systems and stars helps mask the underlying structures.

While ejecting material, the jet acts to move the black holes away from each other, further complicating the orbital paths from a simple elliptical orbit. This further should allow us to calculate the mass of the massive black holes at the center of the galaxy.

Ejections should have a display of Energetic particles throughout the spectrum. The directionality of the emissions and the recapture of some of the mass and energy should be observable once discerned.

As the reference frame between the two black holes changes, the higher energy particles at the front of the jet should be followed by lower energy or more massive particles and then higher energy, creating a structure where the mixing of velocities would add complexity to the momentum profile of the jet.

Photons leaving the black hole would travel at the speed of light and possibly be captured by the causal black hole. Atoms from hydrogen to ununoctium would be

Since 95 percent of the galaxy is low energy mass or black holes it seems that the black holes moving between galaxies would be aggregating mass until they come near another black hole.

With a lifetime of about 13 billion years between formation and cessation of galaxies, we can estimate the capture of a massive black hole by a galaxy which would both disrupt the spiral pattern of formation, and cause the galaxy to collapse upon itself due to the additional mass. We should observe holes where passing black holes collect or steal mass from galaxies but have too high a relative velocity to be captured.

Single Spiral from one

black hole ejecting cloud jet.

Milestones

I. Model Spiral Sprays

Create models for

- Single Black Hole Ejecting
- Dual Ejection
- Single ejection as two black holes pass
- Multiple ejections as two black holes orbit
- Highly elliptical orbit
- Circular orbit with thermal eruptions
- Eruption as temperature equalizes inside black hole
- Contribution of charge to ejecta energy
- Supernova as black hole is reduced below threshold mass

II. Comparison to Observable Data

Explore match between models and visual data

- Galaxies that are spiral
- Center of Galaxies
- Galaxies that are on edge to compare velocities

- Mixing due to multiple black hole events

III. Estimate Revised age of Universe

Trillions of years

The distribution of angular momentum and linear momentum in solar systems is one of the conundrums that is resolved by this theory. Instead of an unknown transfer of angular momentum which creates the gravitational accumulations for the planets and suns, we assume there is a net angular momentum for each cloud generated by the ejection of mass into orbit around the dual black holes.

The formations of disk like spirals is conveniently explained by the spiral created by two bodies periodically ejecting material.

This mass then decays and through distribution we can estimate the age of galaxies, but the novel assumption is that after a period of a few tens of billions of years, a galaxy is aggregated back into supermassive black holes and the cycle starts again.

The expectation would be that outer solar systems in galaxies are older and potentially more massive, but accumulation of dark matter could create a self sustainable generation of new solar systems.

The velocity profiles should be observable from galaxies perpendicular enough to ours to discern the red shift from velocities but still with visible structure.

It is interesting to note some assumptions historically have been that the galaxies are spiralling in, verses our assumption they are spiralling out.

We should be able to estimate the speed of the solar systems in the observed galaxy, and the size or mass, and then the distance between other solar systems to gain a time period. One observation of interest is the symmetry of solar systems on the other side to balance ejecta from the other black hole.

Skew trajectories ?

Mass / Energy concentrations - As volume increases with cube radius increases by linear amount while energy goes up by?

Likely supermassive black holes generate galaxies which in turn indicate location of supermassive black holes.

By definition, lighter particles with the same energy or temperature will have higher velocities. This will give them less exposure to the gravitational field and make them more likely to escape. This leads us to expect that photons, electrons, then protons will escape preferentially, but then as they are depleted, heavier particles will escape.

As the two massive black holes get closer, and the quantum window is open longer, larger jets will escape (and be recaptured by the secondary) resulting in larger solar systems.

As the mass depletes, the black hole will lower in temperature and be thrust back from the orbit.

Need to calculate escape velocity from the binary system. The reentry of particles and mass into the black hole should give out massive amounts of energy according to current theory, potentially causing them to appear as suns.

If we assume a distribution of mass as a gas in equilibrium, the universe is populated by black holes, dark matter (not any special composition, just not glowing hot) and suns. Since luminescent matter represents only five percent of the universe, and planets, moons and asteroids represent one percent of the five percent, ignoring anything other than suns gives less than .0005 /1 error. This means we can look at the average density of the universe as being 20 times greater than the luminescent part and estimate the density of the black holes.

The Boltzmann Distribution of Gas indicates that the Galaxies represented by two or more black holes have an average mass and velocity that should be evenly distributed throughout the universe. If there were a greater density of black holes, they could come into close proximity more often and redistribute their mass, which would be consumed by other passing black holes. After a few trillion years, this would create a Boltzmann Distribution of Black Holes. While the scale is 10^{30} larger than the room scale case, probability doesn't change with scale.

Kinetic energy contained in electrons, protons, and angular momentum all need to be conserved, although in a fixed reference frame the distribution of energy should be uniform.

Since the temperatures are likely in the millions of degrees, and the gravitational pull of the second black hole will redistribute mass as the first black hole in a tidal effect, pressures and flow will make the already complex analysis more convoluted. On the other hand, observational data is effectively smoothed by distance and time, so we can aggregate the effect, even though the exact behavior is likely too complex to model.

Since only 5 percent of the matter in the Universe is luminescent, it is reasonable that the distribution of the other 95 percent has the same velocity and mass distribution, as a MB Gas in equilibrium. On the other hand, the visible centers represented by the binary black holes which emit radiation due to the matter collapsing back into the binary could be indicative that they have greater mass, and the five percent represent the more massive components. This would imply that the cool or dark matter are much denser and higher velocity, since the velocity representing a common temperature of the MB Gas indicates that they are thousands of times higher speed, due to the millions of times lower mass.

This tragic solution to the Fermi Paradox suggests that disruptions in orbital mechanics could be more common than we'd like.

It appears that a very important component of the above scenario relies upon the formation of hot baryonic matter (caveat: the usual astrophysics misnomer for any non-exotic particle, not just baryons). There have been two extensive x-ray sky map surveys that severely constrain the amount of hot gas. Those surveys indicate that the majority of the x-ray emission is from interstellar gas (Bremsstrahlung) with "metal" contributions from Fe lines. This measured emission is also used to estimate dark matter density in addition to galaxy rotation curves, since the energy of the radiating gas is directly affected by the dark matter density which in turn increases the absolute magnitude of the emission and spectrally shifts it.

So the question is, if the gas coming out of a black hole has enough energy to reach escape velocity what would it look like to an observer a few thousand light years away?

1. Solar systems do not appear to form near black holes. At the center of the Coma cluster (one of the best-studied galaxy clusters), the center of the mass can be identified and the nearby stars have quite erratic orbits with no interstellar gas. In our own galaxy, much of the dark matter resides in a halo quite outside the active star formation regions.

There seems to be an assumption that solar systems form rather than a distribution of mass of which above a certain critical mass, would form a solar system. Assuming the Universe is essentially infinitely old, versus 13 billion years give or take, a lot of the mass would be in Brown Dwarfs, and smaller groups where a sun and a solar system never forms. It is reasonable that the black holes would eventually recapture anything in their vicinity so we'd expect things to be far enough away. So what would it look like for a hot gas to leave a pair of black holes? The question is time scale. If we assume that a local cycle is on the order of 13 billion years, what would a bigger cycle look like? What would we see if the other galaxies are randomly in their own cycles?

2. A major obstacle to the above scenario is that there are severe constraints on the total amount of baryonic matter present in the universe. These constraints arise from two lines of reasoning. First, the measured primordial He abundance matches the standard inflation model. Second, the ratio of two of the very precisely measured spectral peaks in

the CMB spectrum are sensitive to the original baryonic density. This baryonic matter constraint must be confronted when proposing that dark, “regular” matter is the source of the measured dark matter - hence the search for exotic particles.

That one is going to take a lot more reading to figure out.

3. There are many types of galaxies known, not just spirals. In the oldest clusters, such as the Coma cluster, there are many elliptical galaxies (possibly between 30-40% by number). Furthermore, these elliptical galaxies appear to primarily consist of “old” stars. That is, stars that have high “metal” content which is a sign of extensive interstellar material recycling. Spiral galaxies, by contrast, are dominated by “young”, low metal-content stars. Even in spiral galaxies the old stars appear concentrated near the central black hole. Perhaps this observation is in accord with your thoughts above. The recent LIGO/Virgo observations have now focussed attention on the formation of heavy elements in binary black hole systems, contrary to the earlier prevailing belief that supernovae were responsible. Too early to tell if that is correct, from what I understand.

The goal is to fit observations, without having more than 3 dimensions and I’m trying to get someone who can run the trillion particle simulators to see what spits out. If the generating black holes have varying orbits, the discharge of matter will be distributed in much more complex ways, especially if there are more than two super black holes.

4. There aren’t very many black holes or black hole pairs in the universe. If their density had been high, then LIGO/Virgo should have detected more. Recent gravitational lensing surveys have likewise placed increasingly strict constraints on the density and mass distributions of black hole pairs. It appears now that the only way to save the “black holes as the missing dark matter” hypothesis is to postulate a very large number of small-sized primordial black holes. Then other problems appear, such as mass limits due to evaporation (small mass) or formation instability (large mass). Once in the realm of pure theory and modeling, though, anything is possible, so there is no apparent consensus yet.

That’s good, or I’d be concerned that there would be x-ray and other sources all over the place. The presence of a pair would be masked by the generating centers of the galaxies. I’m still unclear on the current theories of what’s producing new stars.

5. Dwarf galaxies (few stars, essentially spherical dim objects) are still in contention for non-exotic missing dark matter due to their anomalous measured velocity dispersion. However, the number density seems far too low to contribute significantly based upon the best-measured cases in our own galaxy.

The thought here (not mine, I just can't remember where I read it) was that brown dwarfs could contribute to the dark matter issue but they would be older than 13 Billion years, so by default they can't exist.

6. Challenging the current estimates of the universe's age is difficult due to the very well established measured recession velocities. The scenario above seems to suggest that there should be a distribution of galaxy cluster recession velocities but there doesn't appear to be one. That is, only a few galaxies in our local group are blue-shifted whereas nearly everything else is red-shifted. Perhaps this effect requires some general relativity modeling.

This is one of the biggest issues. We need to figure out how much of an effect of distance / gravity would cause a red shift that seems to be the biggest 'incontrovertible' fact of the big bang. If we could show that there is a nice reasonably small (because it certainly can't be measured in the lab or local space) shift when you are passing through gravity from objects 6 billion light years apart, then the whole theory no longer has a leg.

There are a lot of things that get simpler if we can assume more uniform distributions, no singularities, and no multiple dimensions. The problem is that red shift and the fact that everyone knows something.

My approach is to try to explain things with observation and things we can show.

As the spray is ejected the gravitational force of the black hole it is passing creates an angular momentum (frame dragging) that eventually will cause solar systems to form as the spray cools down.

This takes billions of years.

Inside the belly of the beast.

The pressure of energy inside the black hole would create all sorts of particles with any range of densities. With light, microwave energy and mass all compressed the probabilities would change versus outside the black hole and cook up all sorts of particles.

<https://www-nds.iaea.org/relnsd/vcharthtml/VChartHTML.html>

It is informative to look at the stable isotopes, and their abundance, but other than note that the bigger black holes are likely to be able to create a larger quantity of heavier particles, unless the half life is more than a few billion years, then only the stable ones will remain. But it is interesting to think that uranium might be the residue of much heavier particles.

When the event horizon is breached, by the opposing gravitational field of the other black hole, the plasma of superheated isotopes would be repelled by the charge, pressure, and centrifugal forces.

It is interesting to ponder where the distribution would be in terms of mass, as the rotation of the black hole would act like a centrifuge, while the gravity would pull the heavier isotopes inward.

This would likely mix the species as pressure gradients change with the release of material.

This would both propel the black holes away from each other, and emit a burst of material.

The material would disperse initially due to the charges, and then accumulate electrons and start to form masses.

Light would likely not leak out as much from the relatively small aperture momentarily opening. When it did, it should look like a burst, but then quickly red shift down, as it feels the gravitational attraction of two black holes.

The shear from the gravity of the orbiting black holes would impart some rotational momentum around the center of gravity of the ejected mass. Billions of years later that would form the solar systems, as the masses balance rotational momentum with gravitational attraction.

It is overwhelming to think of an eruption that has the entire mass of a solar system happening in a relatively short period.

The mass and distance between the black holes would change over time until the dispersion and accretion of the system results in the merging of the black holes.

Light and Gradients

Light is the most well understood of all the forms of matter and energy. It's behavior, creation and extinction are reliably controlled, to the point where we can apply an electric field to a crystal and across a boundary, light will be emitted from Diodes.

On the other side, as predicted by Einstein, solar cells absorb photons and across similar band gaps are absorbed and an electron released at a higher potential.

When passed through a material, the wave equation reliably predicts the path the photons will take, and through two slits, we can build a statistical model that reliably models the interference patterns observed since Newton studied them in 1666.

But the rationale of why light is formed is more subtle. We can say it is a change in the field between two dipoles.

So the fields themselves are not the cause of light being emitted but the change of the field over time, with the greater the change and the shorter the period of change, the higher the energy of the photon.

These waves can be extremely long and low energy or extremely short and high energy.

While we have the most experience with generating radio waves, heat and light, with more recently xrays and higher energy forms.

But the perspective is usually focused on the wave and not the gradient field.

This is problematic as it suggests that while atoms are dipoles and all of our experience is changing the fields between atoms through various electromechanical systems, that changing the gradient of a gravitational field should work equally well.

Except other than firing two projectiles near each other at a fraction of the speed of light, so they come within a few mm, it's unclear how you'd modulate a gravitational field.

Since the relationship of gravitational fields is

$F \sim GMm/\text{distance squared}$

We can change the distance with a velocity V and obtain a pulse, but other than satisfy curiosity there isn't much of a point.

Due to the predictability of light, we can infer that it does not just change direction without some field change.

Whether this is through a crystalline material or glass, we have a fit with model and math and observed reality.

The question is can we create a field strong enough to manipulate light outside a molecule?

Since field strength of a dipole is proportional to the charge over the distance, while single charges don't seem a lot in our intuition, when the distances are nanometers and femtometers, the fields are exceptionally large.

It is difficult to scale charges by billions of times to create macroscopic fields on the orders of microns.

The billions of billions of electrons needed would jump to other objects and distribute the charge.

But we can estimate the lattice spacing and charges on the crystals in an LED or LASER, and calculate the change in field needed.

In a molecule the alignment of the atoms can create alignment in the fields, and corresponding alignment in the light emitted. This polarization gives rise to many of the attributes of Lasers.

Monopoles such as gravity should have similar attributes, but in most cases the fields are orders of magnitude smaller, and the field gradients are equally small.

Except light always has a very high velocity.

So when it encounters a field gradient, the change over time is extremely high. Not as high as between molecules or the electron and nucleus, but it is reasonable that it could emit a very low energy photon in response.

The real question subject to rigorous development of the model, is could the emission of the low energy photon

1. Lower the energy of the photon
2. Change the direction of the 'scattered' photon
3. Behave in a manner consistent with observation

If the emission of photons would swing the photon around a massive object, it would explain the gravitational lensing, but would need to show a substantial redshift during this action, due to the released photons.

We should see more redshift as the light passes closer to the gravitational source.

The math should show that the emitted photon is along the R direction in spherical coordinates of the gravity field.

The energy of the photon should be proportional to the energy required to change the momentum of a photon.

If we can explain momentum change and redshift as part of this field photon interaction it simplifies the models greatly.

Atomic Gravitometer

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-018-30608-1>

Formation of Black Holes

(And their dissolution)

The photoelectric effect was Einstein's 1921 Nobel Prize winning realization that photons excite the electron into an excited state, and later work with lasers has even stripped all the electrons from the nuclei for brief intervals.

The charged nuclei have increased spacing versus the electrically neutral example of the same isotope.

As a sun converts hydrogen and other atoms into denser materials, the temperature increases and produces light from the interaction of atoms at high energy converting thermal and mechanical energy into light.

The core of the star might be millions of degrees, but the photons could take many years to escape as they collide, are sometimes absorbed and reemitted, and eventually through brownian motion reach the surface, so although hotter, the core doesn't emit light, rather most comes from the surface which is only a few thousand degrees Kelvin in most cases.

The photons though can excite electrons which have a mass of $9.1093837 \times 10^{-31}$ kilograms. The exit velocity of a star is given by

$$v_{\text{esc}} = \text{Square root of } \sqrt{2GM/r}$$

This allows us to estimate the temperature, density, size and other attributes of suns from millions of lightyears away, comparing the output from multiple isotopes such as hydrogen, helium, sodium and others.

As a sun grows hotter, the electrons are further excited, which should increase the size of the sun with temperature. The Sun is actually more than 3 times less dense than the average density of the earth due to the heat and charges.

An observed consequence is the Solar Wind https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Solar_wind which gradually reduces the mass of the star.

For a few stellar objects, they encounter more mass and grow.

As the mass of the sun reaches a critical stage, the gravitational attraction increases as more mass is absorbed.

The Schwarzschild radius https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Schwarzschild_radius is defined as

$$r_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2},$$

Where the gravitational attraction below that radius is high enough that the escape velocity exceeds the speed of light, so any particle would remain trapped.

This means that if electrons are expelled, on the capture of particles, instead of the star swelling due to charge forces the internal photons, electrons, and nuclei are trapped inside.

This is particularly interesting as we explore the possibility of leaking electrons in a black hole, especially rotating ones.

There could be a runaway effect where the neutrons are captured that are normally part of the cosmic radiation of any star.

But as the star increases in density, the neutrons are kept within the star, helping to form dense nuclei.

With a half-life of approximately 10.2 minutes, neutrons can be captured by other nuclei as they pass through the coulomb barrier not having a charge to be repelled by the electrons or protons.

If the velocity of the neutron is slow enough it will decay into a proton and a small amount of energy and capture an electron and become hydrogen.

If it encounters a nucleus, it will make a heavier isotope.

And some of the protons in the nucleus under rare conditions capture electrons and decay into a short lived neutron.

Normally this process is very one directional, but given sufficient gravity, and capturing of neutrons unable to escape, the probability of heavier and heavier isotopes being produced and the stellar mass shrinking instead of expanding becomes possible.

Once the threshold is reached, the mass condenses, as heavier elements are produced, further reducing the Schwarzschild radius and a black hole condenses and becomes more stable.

This makes the black hole much more long lived than a normal star of the same mass.

While the stars go through lifetimes of billions of years, and smaller stars even longer, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stellar_evolution there is no reason for a black hole to ever decay unless it reaches another black hole.

Heavy Elements

The above mechanisms for capturing neutrons and creating a spectrum of increasing density would produce a wide assortment of isotopes with the lifetimes of some of them promoting growth, and the production of intermediate densities as most of them break down.

The Nuclide table, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nuclide> shows the possible combinations of electrons and nuclei.

Observing the lifetimes and the relative abundance of each nuclide creates a problem, in that there is no observable mechanism to account for the heavier elements.

A handwaving explanation of supernova creating heavier elements, and then they are distributed through the universe is suspect in that while the mechanism for production is

Coming full circle

The hum in the universe that is predicted by this model has been found as a constant background noise, when two stellar black holes violently eject the mass of a solar system in a single event. This bang might not be 'Big' or rip the fabric of space, but it's likely to be observable from any distance.

The gravitational waves from the two bodies changing momentum (black hole and ejecta) would appear as the two black holes reach their closest point of approach and the gravitational attraction effectively cancels out the Shwartzchild barrier.

But the orbits would be in the order of years to thousands of years between these approaches, so we'd expect them to be noticeable as huge events.

Unless they happen to a billion celestial objects evenly distributed around the universe, in which case if the average was every 30 years or billion seconds we'd detect one a second.

If they were distributed in a uniform manner in every direction (validating another part of the quasi steady state model) then we'd expect a standard distribution from huge and close to small and distant. Since waves in a 3D medium dissipate as they propagate with the inverse square law, the more distant objects would be fainter and closer objects more noticeable.

In conjunction there should be bursts of light for tiny fractions of a second, as the material passes through the hole in the Swartzchild barrier. From cosmic rays to simply hot gas, it would almost immediately cool down, but for that brief opening, the temperature would be millions of degrees. To instruments looking for stars, this would appear as noise also.

The light would come out of nowhere and be gone as it cools almost instantly. In some cases it could be what is currently thought of as a pulsar. In other cases being distant and brief it would be discarded as flashes of noise.

Correlating these flashes with the gravitational wave would be ideal as it would be expected to propagate along the same path.

Now that we have identified many gravitational lenses, we can look for both along those directions, with the timing of the gravitational noise being replicated by the flashes, synchronized as each is resolved from a different path of the original image and the redshifts should correlate into a pattern.

The key is to not have any bias as to the cause of the redshift, or noise, and let the numbers fall where they lay.